

Recycle of Polyester/Cotton Mixed Yarn as Reinforcement of Hybrid Composite Material

Teruo KIMURA, Hiroki HANAMITSU
Kyoto Institute of Technology
Matsugasaki, Sakyo-ku, Kyoto 606-8585, Japan
tkimura@kit.ac.jp

SUMMARY

Compression molding of hybrid composites by using the waste of Pet/Cotton mixed yarn as reinforcement was carried out and the mechanical properties of molded composites were discussed. As a result, the fairly high strength, modulus and Izod impact value could be obtained for the molded hybrid composites with PP matrix.

Keywords: Recycle of Pet/Cotton mixed yarn, Hybrid composites, Compression molding

INTRODUCTION

In order to make a sustainable society, it is necessary to develop effective utilization of all sorts of wastes. One of the major wastes from our living is fiber wastes. Fiber wastes are generally divided to nonindustrial and industrial wastes, and in total, two million ton/year domestically thrown out in Japan. Nowadays, recycling rate of these fiber wastes are only about 10. In recent years, fiber wastes that consist of single material such as Pet and Nylon fibers have come to be recycled as a plastic molding material. However, mixed fiber wastes are difficult to separate to single material, which is the problem of advancing fiber recycling. Thus, the beneficial use of mixed fiber wastes without separation is required. In this paper, the recyclability of mixed yarn as reinforcement of hybrid composite materials was discussed.

MATERIALS USED

Aspect of mixed yarn used here is shown in Fig.1. This mixed yarn (Kurabo industries Ltd., 421 dtex) consists of Pet and cotton fibers in mixing ratio of 3:7. The diameter, length and strength are 13.3 μ m, 18.3mm, 666MPa for Pet fiber and 14.9 μ m, 14.2mm, 367MPa for cotton fiber, respectively. Widely used resin, PP, was used as matrix material.

MOLDING METHOD OF COMPOSITES

For preforming, carding machine was used to gain web by carding and mixing PP staples and Pet/cotton mixed yarn as shown in Fig.2. Figure 3 shows the aspect of web after carding process. By repeating the carding process, Pet and cotton fibers were found separate and homogeneously-mixed in the web. The perform(web) was heated

and compressed between flat dies with 4mm spacing as shown in Fig.4. Molding temperature was set to 185 degree in consideration of the melting temperature of PP, 165 degree. After 15 min. heating, the die was cooled by air under the compressive force. Volume fraction of mixed yarns (V_f) was varied up to 60% in volume.

Now, the deterioration tests of cotton fiber were done before compression molding to verify the effect of heating temperature. Aspects of tensile test and size of test specimen of cotton fiber are shown in Fig. 5.

EXPERIMENTAL METHOD

The aspects of Pet/cotton mixed web and the cross section of molded composites were studied by using scanning electron microscope(SEM, Hitachi S-3000, Tokyo, Japan).

The molded composites were cut to strip specimens and evaluated for mechanical properties. Tensile tests were carried out under test speed of 5mm/min using AUTO GRAPH AG-I5kN apparatus. And Izod impact value was also measured. Apparatus and shape of test specimens are shown in Fig.6.

RESULTS

The results of tensile strength and modulus of cotton fiber are shown in Fig.7. The figure indicates that the strength of cotton fibers degraded to 20 %, 48% due to the molding temperatures such as 185 and 205 for 15min., respectively. Thus it may be concluded that the molding temperature and time greatly affect the mechanical properties of composites. On the other hand, the tensile modulus keeps almost same value against the temperature and heating time. As mentioned above, the compression molding temperature here is 165 and is reasonable for the cotton fiber.

Figure 8 shows the aspect of cross section of composites with various volume fraction of mixed yarn. Good dispersion of mixed yarn can be seen for the specimens of $V_f=20\%$ and 40% . However, the pull out of the fiber occurs at many places because of the lack of adhesion between fiber and PP matrix. Especially the lack of resin can be seen for $V_f=60\%$ because of the excess of fibers.

The results of tensile tests of composites are shown in Fig.9. The tensile modulus was calculated from the initial part of strain-stress curve in which the curve is liner. As seen in the figure, the tensile strength and modulus are improved by addition of mixed yarn and take highest value at $V_f=40\%$ which is about 200% compared with that of PP matrix.

Figure 10 shows the Izod impact value of composites. The Izod impact value also increases with increasing volume fraction of mixed yarn, and take highest value at $V_f=40\%$. It is noted here that the value is tenth the value of PP matrix.

In this study, cotton fiber which is brittle and Pet fiber which is ductile were used as reinforcement. Figure 11 shows the stress-strain curves for the hybrid composite together with the result for cotton composite. Thus there may be effects of using both the fibers. Namely, the strength and fracture elongation improved due to the inclusion of

Pet fiber for the hybrid composite. Figure 12 shows the hybrid effect for the Izod impact value. As is shown in the figure that the fairly larger impact value can be obtained for the hybrid composite compared with that for cotton composite. This fact may be caused by the ductile property of PET fiber containing in the hybrid composite.

CONCLUSION

In this study, we investigate the molding process and mechanical properties of hybrid composites. Pet/cotton mixed yarn were used as reinforcement. As results, PP resins were reinforced and because of Pet fiber usage, the composite had ductile properties. It may be concluded that the molding process suggested in this paper is effective for recycling mixed fiber wastes.

PET/cotton fiber (PET 30% , cotton 70%)

Fig.1 Pet/Cotton mixed yarn

Fig.2 Molding of PET/cotton/PP web

Fig.3 Aspect of Pet/cotton mixed web after carding process

Fig.4 Compression molding method of composite

Fig.5 Tensile test of cotton fiber

Fig.6 Tensile and Impact tests of composites

Fig.7 Tensile properties of cotton fiber

Fig.8 Aspect of cross section of composites

Fig.9 Tensile properties of composites

Fig.10 Izod impact value

Fig. 11 Stress-Strain curve of composite

Fig.12 Izod impact value of composites